

Use of plasticized Portland cement

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Annotation: *Plasticized cement differs from the usual by the fact that the concrete mix made from it is extremely well spread.*

Key words: *sulfuric acid anhydride, dry matter, concentrated aqueous solution*

Plasticized portland cement is a hydraulic binder that is formed from a very fine paste together with a compound that plasticizes portland cement clinker. Gypsum is added when the plasticized portland cement is adjusted to change the biting times as needed. No more than 3% of sulfuric acid (CO_3) in gypsum cement should be added.

Sulfate-alcohol bard (s.s.b.) concentrate is used as a plasticizing compound. S.s.b. from 0.1 to 0.25% by weight of cement (in dry matter).

Sulfite-alcohol bar can be added to the cement in the form of a dry substance or a concentrated aqueous solution.

Plasticized Portland cement should have the same fineness, flat size, bending times and strength as ordinary Portland cement. Plasticized Portland Cement 300; 400; 500; Produced in 600 brands.

Plasticized cement differs from the usual by the fact that the concrete mix made from it is extremely well spread.

Sulfite-alcohol bar can strengthen well due to the plasticizing effect in general: increasing the plasticity of cement paste (concrete) allows to reduce the amount of water poured without changing the plasticity (good placement) of the mixture, resulting in increased density of cement stone.

The use of plasticizers also improves a number of other technical properties of concrete. In particular, cold resistance increases, humidity decreases. This is mainly due to the formation of more dense cement. This is aided by a decrease in S / T_s .

Plasticized Portland cement is used in the construction of concrete and reinforced concrete structures, both above and below ground, as well as in water. When preparing a building mix, it is necessary to add clay, lime, slag to use plasticized cements.

Plasticized Portland cement can also be used in the production of precast concrete and reinforced concrete structures.

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